

POULTRY MARKET SUPPLY RESPONSE OF POULTRY EGG PRODUCERS IN FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY, ABUJA, NIGERIA

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<https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.032606010.04>

Abstract

Background information on the determinants of market forces in poultry egg (PE) marketing aids production cost adjustment by establishing the price at which suppliers are willing to supply eggs to consumers through the knowledge of market surplus; however, access to this information is limited. Thus, this study examined the market supply response of PE producers. The marketable and marketed surplus (MS) of the poultry was determined, and the determinants and elasticities of the PE were estimated. Structured questionnaire was used to obtain data following a multistage sampling technique. Three area councils-Kuje, Kwali, and Bwari were purposively selected due to the concentration of PE farmers. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics- multiple regression analysis, the marketable and MS was determined, and the elasticities were estimated. The result showed farmers' mean age-40 years and household size-4persons. Eighty-percent of the farmers were males, 86% were married, and most of the producers (93.3%, 73.3%, 83.3% and 80%) were constrained by the high cost of production, poor roads, inadequate startup capital and unfavourable government policies, respectively. The marketable-83,326crates and MS -83,295creates were calculated. The MS elasticity was unitary. The coefficient of R^2 was 0.71. The results revealed that the annual output, employed labour, management system, experience and unit price positively and significant influenced the MS; conversely, losses, quantity consumed at home, gifts, and distance from the market negatively impact the MS. The study recommends the availability of credit facilities at a single-digit rate and farmers' social groups' formation.

Keywords: Supply response, poultry egg, producers, FCT Abuja

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been increasing demand for poultry products in Nigeria, but the demand trends do not match the local production (Herrero, et al., 2014; Mammo and Beyene,

2022). Poultry bird count globally is about 16.2 billion, with 71.6% in developing countries, turning out 68,000,000 tons of meat and 58,000,000 tons of eggs; (Hundie, et al., 2019; Komolafe, et al., 2023).

Poultry egg is an important product loved by people of all races. It is the most widely demanded poultry product (Mohammed, et al., 2018). Poultry egg production is an important part of farming in Nigeria, which occupies a prime position for improving animal protein consumption in both rural and urban households (Ajetomobi and Adepoju, 2010; Nasiru, et al., 2012; Nordhagen and Klemm, 2018). It serves for food production and additional occupation to supplement the income of small and marginal farm families (Ekunweand et al., 2009; Nasiru et al., 2012; Komolafe et al., 2023). It is a potentially strong catalyst of enterprise and economic development and has been described as the fastest means of bridging the protein deficiency gap prevailing in the country. One of the development challenges facing most developing countries, like Nigeria, is their inability to feed their ever-growing population with adequate calories and protein (Adedeji et al., 2013; Komolafe, et al., 2023).

Eggs are a major source of animal protein in the human diet and are affordable to poor people (Aboki et al., 2013). The high nutrient content of eggs and their low-calorie value have made them widely accepted as a natural commodity to meet consumers' demand. Poultry eggs were always in high demand as they serve as a major ingredient in baking, beverages and the food industry at large. It is a source of income for both small and large-scale producers. Despite the positive features of poultry eggs, the supply is low and seems to be beyond the reach of an average Nigerian,

especially in the study area. This decrease is due to certain factors that influence the supply of poultry eggs. Hence, it becomes necessary to examine the market supply response and its determinants. Supply response can be said to be a dynamic concept that represents a change in agricultural output due to a change in the output price (Tripathi and Prasad, 2009; Manyeki, et al., 2021.). Although there are many farmers involved in poultry egg production in Abuja, they still cannot keep pace with the demand of the ever-growing population. As highly nutritious as eggs are, they remain scarce and expensive in Nigeria, with an annual supply of 69 eggs per person per year, (FAOSTAT, 2013), as cited in Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition (GAIN, 2019) This can be explained by factors influencing the cost of production and supply, which leads to the increase in the price of the product. Price is the major determinant of supply of poultry eggs to the market, and adjusting the poultry production cost will contribute to the willingness of the producers to supply poultry eggs (Sumner et al., 2011; Akintunde, et al., 2015; Ashrit, 2021).), Also, price fluctuation affects the market supply response of poultry eggs since the supply of eggs increases as the market price increases and vice versa.

Understanding and having the background knowledge of the primary determinants of market supply and demand of poultry eggs would positively adjust the production cost, hence affecting the price at which producers are willing to supply poultry eggs to consumers. This necessitated this study. An

increase in the marketed surplus, accompanied by favourable market prices will improve the egg farmers' income level in Abuja. Also, the information on market supply response with emphasis on marketed surplus, seems limited, especially in the study area. The main objective of this study was to examine the market response of poultry egg producers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. The specific objectives include: describing the socioeconomic characteristics of the poultry egg producers in the study area, identifying the marketable and marketed surplus of poultry egg production, ascertaining the extent to which the farm characteristics affect the marketable surplus of egg production, estimating the elasticity of the marketed surplus, and identifying the constraints faced by egg producers.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, which is the capital of Nigeria. It is also the central region of Nigeria and is bounded to the north by Kaduna State, to the east by Nassarawa State and to the west by Niger State. The Federal Capital Territory is situated between the latitudes 9° 6' 10" N and longitude 7° 19' 52" E and has an area of 2824 miles (7315sq km) with an estimated population of 1,406,239 persons (Federal Capital

Territory Administration (FCTA), 2023; National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2023)

FCT is divided into six area councils, which are: Abuja Municipal, Gwagwalada, Abaji, Kuje, Bwari and Kwali.

2.1 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A multistage sampling technique was used in the selection of the respondents; 3 area councils-Kuje, Kwali and Bwari were purposively selected due to the predominance of poultry egg farmers in the areas. The list of existing poultry egg farmers was collected from the Ministry of Agriculture in Abuja. From the list, 90 poultry egg farmers were randomly selected from each of the three area councils, thus giving a sample size of 270 respondents for the study.

Primary data was collected with a well-structured questionnaire. Descriptive statistics, frequency, and mean were used to describe the characteristics of the egg farmers. Marketable and marketed surplus analysis was used to determine the actual supply response. The surplus analysis as presented is based on the steps of (Krishna Raj, 1962; Roiter, Eremeeva, Roiter, and Vedenkina, (2021).

$$MS = P - R$$

Where MS = the marketable surplus
P = the total egg production
R = the total consumption or utilization of poultry egg

The marketed surplus analysis is given as;

$$MT = MS + PS - L$$

Where MT = marketed surplus

MS = marketable surplus

PS = past stock

L = losses during packaging and transit of the marketable surplus left for sale.

Regression analysis was used to determine the effect of the farm characteristics on the marketable surplus. The model stated thus:

$$Y = F(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4, X_5, X_6, X_7, X_8, E_i)$$

Where,

Y = marketed surplus of poultry egg

F = constant

X1 = employed labour (no of persons employed)

X2 = annual output (crates)

X3 = management system (dummy: deep litter system = 0, battery cage system = 1, battery cage and deep litter system = 2)

X4 = flock size (number)

X5 = farming experience (years)

X6 = distance from market (km)

X7 = losses (crates)

X8 = unit price per crate (naira)

E_i = error term

The apriori expectation is stated as thus:

$$Y_i = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + b_7X_7 + b_8X_8$$

The elasticity of supply formula, as presented based on the steps of Krishna Raj (1962) was used to estimate the marketed surplus of the poultry egg;

$$E_i = b_i$$

Where E_i is the elasticity coefficient
 is the average total production
 is the average marketed surplus.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Socioeconomic and Farm Characteristics of Poultry Egg Producers

The socio-economic and farm characteristics of the poultry egg farmers are shown in Table 1. The result denotes that the majority of the poultry egg producers (80%) were males and 20% females. This shows that the egg producers are dominated by males, which is in line with the findings of (Ayinde et al. (2012) who said in their work in Ogun State, that male producers were popular in the area. From Table 1, it is seen that 83.3% of the poultry egg

producers fall within the age bracket of 30-50 years, while 6.67% were less than 30 with an average age of 40 years. This showed that they are young farmers who can commit energy to production activities and are economically active, which is in line with the findings of Mohamed et al.(2013) and Ayinde et al. (2012) who stated that poultry egg producers that fall within their middle age were still in their active labor stage and invariably increased the volume of egg production, given their labour input. The result of marital status reveals that the majority (86.6%) of the poultry egg producers were married with an educational level of (93.3%) and a family size of 1 – 4 persons and a mean of 4 persons. This showed that almost all the farmers received formal education and had nuclear families, which consisted of parents and children, excluding extended families. Education enhances production as well as increase egg supply to the market and family size and large household size increases the quantity of eggs consumed and hence reduce marketed surplus. The farming experience result showed that the majority (62.3%) of the respondents had 1–10 years of farming experience and a mean of 11 years, which indicates that the farmers in the area had been in production for a long time. The findings on management systems revealed that 50% of the farmers adopted battery cages, 15% deep litter and 25% both, This indicates that producers use battery cage systems more because it seems to be the best management technique for higher production and saves poultry egg losses. This is in line with the findings of Ayinde et al. (2012) who stated that the production of battery cage systems is more popular than the other systems.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of the Socioeconomic characteristics of the Poultry egg producers

Socio-economic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean
Gender			
Male	72	80	
Female	18	20	
Age (years)			
Less than 30	6	6.67	
30 – 50	75	83.30	40 years
Above 50	9	10.00	
Total	90	100	
Marital status			
Married	78	86.6	
Single	12	13.3	
Total	90	100	
Educational level			
0	6	6.70	
1 – 6	12	13.33	12 years
7 – 12	30	33.33	
13 – 17	42	46.66	
Total	90	100	
Household size			
1 – 4	30	33.33	4 persons
5 – 8	39	43.30	
9 – 12	21	23.33	
Total	90	100	
Farming experience			
1 – 10	57	63.33	
11 – 20	30	32.33	11 years
21 – 30	03	3.30	
Total	90	100	
Management system			
Battery cage	45	50	
Deep litter	24	27	
Combination (battery cage and deep litter)	21	23	
Total	90	100	

Source: Field survey data, 2023

3.2. Marketable and marketed surplus of Poultry Egg Producers in Abuja

The result of the marketable and marketed surplus, as shown in Table 2 showed that poultry eggs were mostly for sale, and a small quantity is usually kept for consumption. However, with an increase in production, more quantity would be sold as

a decrease in poultry egg production will lead to a decrease in the sale of poultry eggs. Also, when poultry eggs were utilized for home consumption or given out as gifts, the marketed surplus is reduced and losses incurred in the poultry egg production are due to poor management systems.

Table 2: Marketable And Marketed Surplus of Poultry Egg Producers

	Variables	Amount (crates)
I	Total production	83424
ii	Utilization	
	Home consumption	32
	Quantity given as gift	66
	Sub total	98
iii	Marketable surplus (i – ii)	83326
Iv	Losses	61
V	Past stock	30
Vi	Subtotal (iii + v)	83356
Vii	Marketed surplus (vi - iv)	83,295

Source: Field Survey 2013

Marketable surplus (Ms):

$$\text{Average total output} = \frac{2502728}{30} = 83424 \text{ crates}$$

$$\text{Average quantity consumed at home} = \frac{972}{30} = 32 \text{ crates}$$

$$\text{Average quantity given out as gift} = \frac{1966}{30} = 66 \text{ crates}$$

$$MT = MS + Ps - L$$

$$\text{Average past stock} = \frac{900}{30} = 30 \text{ crates}$$

$$\text{Quantity lost} = \frac{1826}{30} = 61 \text{ crates}$$

$$MT = 83326 + 30 - 61 = 83295 \text{ crates}$$

$$MT = 83295 \text{ crates}$$

3.3. Effects of farm characteristics of poultry egg producers on the marketed surplus of poultry eggs

A multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the impact of farm factors on the marketable excess of eggs in FCT Abuja, incorporating four functional forms into the regression model. The result showed that the double log (meaning the natural log of the dependent and independent variables was taken before the regression analysis was carried out, unlike the semi-log or exponential, where only the explanatory variables were log. For the linear function, both the dependent and independent variables were not log function gave the best fit, as the coefficient of multiple determinations R^2 and adjusted R^2 were 0.71 and 0.699, respectively. These values were the highest for the four functional form therefore, the double log was the best equation model. It means 71% of the marketed surplus of poultry eggs was explained by the variables included in the

model, while the remaining 29% was due to stochastic error. The prob > F is significant at 1%; this implies that the whole model was statistically significant. From the multiple regression result, the coefficients of employed labour ($p < 0.1$), annual output ($p < 0.001$), management system ($p < 0.001$), and unit price ($p < 0.001$) were positive, while distance from market ($p < 0.001$), and losses ($p < 0.1$). This implied that employed labour, annual output, management system and unit price had a direct effect on the marketed surplus of poultry eggs in the study area and a unit increase in the above coefficients will lead to a proportionate increase in the marketed surplus of poultry eggs by the level of their significance, while distance from market and losses would increase the marketed surplus of poultry eggs by the percentages of their significance. However, a conclusion can be drawn that the poultry egg producers' farm characteristics had a significant influence on the marketed surplus.

Table 3: Effect of farm characteristics of poultry egg producers on the marketed surplus of poultry egg

Variable	Linear	Semi log	Double log	Exponential resume
Constant	52.20 (0.51)	-4053 (-756)	0.63 (1.95)	3465 (1.37)
Employed labour	5.848 (3.108)	18805.279 (1.645)	0.401* (0.05)	-1559* (-0.093)
Annual output	0.99 (11.00)	8610 (12.77)	0.120*** (0.001)	1.00 (93.15)
Management system	31.61 (2.305)**	-15461.64 (1.507)	(2.539) *** 0.000E-03	1160 (0.902)
No of birds	-0.457 (1.010)	-1.176 (0.811)	3.28E-0.05 (0.72)	-7651 (-1.188)
Experience	1.858 (1.408)	-1119.027 (0.117)	0.905 (0.000)	31.215 (0.319)
Distance of market	-1891 (2.938)**	7927.18 (0.822)	(-4.230) *** 0.001	-5.561 (-0.410)
Losses	-1.346 (4.952)*	-4852 (0.631) *	(-3.949) * 0.01	-1.047E-125 (0.238)
Unit price	-0.089 (0.579)	-40240.775 (0.487)	(2.037) *** 0.001	-1.806E-019 (0.238)
R^2	0.68	0.69	0.71	0.66
Adjusted R	0.65	0.66	0.699	0.65
F_{cal}	0.018	0.026	0.0388	0.012

*= 10% **= 5% ***= 1% $P > t_s$ were in parenthesis

Source: field survey, 2023

3.4. Elasticity of marketed surplus

The market supply response of farmers in terms of the elasticity of the marketed surplus with respect to output is presented in Table 4. The result showed that the elasticity of the market surplus was positive and unitary, this indicates that a 100%

change in price will bring about a 100% change in the market surplus. The elasticity of poultry egg output is unity, showing that the output of egg would change by as the much percentage change in the number of birds.

Table 4: Elasticity of marketed surplus

Elasticity of marketable surplus with respects to output	Elasticity coefficient
Output of Poultry egg	1.00

$$E_i b_i = \frac{\Delta b_i}{b_i} \div \frac{\Delta P_i}{P_i}$$

$$b_i = 1.00$$

- = Average total output = 83424 creates

- = Marketed surplus of egg = 83295

$$E_i = 1.000 \frac{83424}{83295}$$

$$= 1.00 (1.00)$$

$$E_i = 1$$

3.5. Constraints faced by poultry egg producers

Multiple responses and the percentage distribution of constraints faced by poultry egg producers is shown in Table 5. The result showed that the majority of the respondents (93.3%), (73.3%), (60%) and (80%) complained of the high cost of production (mean=3.52) due to the high cost of input, poor transportation (mean=3.20) due to bad roads (mean=3.01) and poor conditions of

vehicles increased the cost of transportation of eggs to the market and unfavourable government policies towards egg production. These problems have consequences on the marketed surplus of poultry eggs; for instance, poor transportation and high cost of transportation lead to broken and damaged eggs, resulting in a reduction. The mean values of the variables indicated the level of severity, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Constraints faced by poultry egg producers

Constraints	Frequency*	Percentage (%)	Mean	Rating
Inadequate capital	25	83.3	3.51	Severe
Poor feeder roads	22	73.3	3.01	Severe
High cost of transportation	16	53.3	3.20	Severe
High cost of production	28	93.3	3.52	Severe
High taxation	26	86.7	2.23	Not Severe
Price fluctuation	18	60.0	2.79	Not Severe
Unfavourable Government policies	24	80.0	2.90	Not Severe
Lack of storage facilities	10	33.3	2.7	Not Severe

Source: field survey, 2023

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, it can be concluded that the respondents were mainly married, educated, had a modest family size, and were of active age and experienced, hence enhancing their capacity for company survival; thus, their ability to survive in the business. The findings indicated that the producers' farm characteristics significantly influenced the marketed surplus of eggs. The primary challenges faced by the producers included high production costs, elevated transportation expenses, substantial taxation, insufficient capital, adverse government policies, and inadequate feeder roads.

The results of this research have some policy implications for development in Agriculture. Based on the aforementioned conclusions, the following recommendations. If implemented will improve the market supply of poultry eggs

in the area. The government should assist poultry egg producers in solving their input and credit facilities constraints to improve their output and consequently marketable and market surplus. It is further recommended that the poultry egg producers should form a viable marketing association and cooperative societies to help in the easy transfer of information, stabilizing poultry egg prices, increasing the chances of obtaining loans from private sectors (financial institutions) which were identified constraint in the study and therefore benefiting from various governments and non-governmental organization farm credit schemes to boost the egg business. Also, efforts should be made towards the provision of infrastructural facilities such as good roads and standard vehicles that would help in reducing transportation costs and the easy transporting of the egg to the markets to reduce losses.

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